

Use of E-resources by Undergraduate Students of Meenakshi Medical College Hospital & Research Institute, Kanchipuram, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

The article is aims to evaluate and review the revelation of ICT and the usage of e-resources by the U.G students of MMCHRI medical College, MAHER University, Enathur, Tamil Nadu, with an analysis to identify the revelation of ICT and electronic resources by the students of U.G courses on their department or at library. Moreover, study aims to emphasize the problems found by the U.G students and suggests some remedial measures for its improvement. The researcher investigated the usage of e-resources through a survey based on a structured questionnaire. The study confirmed that students of Medical College are aware of the E-Resources and utilize of different types of e-databases, e-resources, and e-journals. It has recommends for the increase in the access facilities with provide high internet speed and subscribe to more e-resources for the users.

Keywords: Information communication technology, e-resources, e-journal, internet, Usage pattern, Medical science students

Introduction

Meenakshi Medical College Hospital & Research Institute, Enathur, Kanchipuram District, Tamil Nadu is the constituent college of MAHER Universtiy established in the year, 2003 with the aim to strengthen education and research in the area of Medical education in the state. The quick evolution in information and communication technology (ICT) has brought a radical change in the information circumstances giving rise to a number of options to handle varied information sources expediently, and smoothly. Because a result, e-resources are become the major required after modern library's reserves in satisfying varied needs of students, faculties, and researchers with minimum efforts and in time. Information communication technology has changed the world and it has become one of the most important tools for retrieving the information. The e-information resource has occupied a major portion of library collections. The worth and make use of information resources, especially an e-resources, have improved with the time.

Hence, there was essential to carry out the study on the different features of e-resources and the problems relating to utilize of e-resources by the students, more specifically by the students of education and research universities.

The current study is intended to analyses, utilize of e-resources by the undergraduate students of MMCHRI medical College. This study is purposefully carried out for the upgrading of library services in medical Science subjects.

Literature Review

Various literature studies have been carried out regarding to the revelation of computers and electronic resources use of the students, researchers and faculties of various colleges and universities. Swain & Panda¹ they observed that faculty members have a preference of using e-articles, e-thesis and dissertation over to their printed counterparts.

Internet, electronic mail, and electronic resources are accessed by various organizations in India. Utilize of e-journals are studied by Satpathy & Rout², reveals that faculty members are aware of the e-resources. K.N. Kandpal, S.S. Rawat and K.S.R. Vithal³ to assess and evaluate the revelation of Information Communication Technology and utilize of electronic resources by students of NTR College of Veterinary Science, affiliated to Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University, Gannavaram, A.P. In academic libraries has to play a role as doorway of electronic resources and it provides support in access of these e-resources. Students are mostly dependents on these e-resources for their necessary information and to remain up to date in their subject. In this aspect the more quantity of computers should be increased in the library for accessing the e-resources. This study expose that the students of NTR College of Veterinary Science are utilizing the available electronic resources adequately. At present there is adequate scope for libraries are developing its infrastructure facilities providing its services and procurement of more electronic resources particularly in the area of Veterinary Science. Presently there is adequate scope for the library to develop its infrastructural facilities for providing the services and procurement of more e-resources particularly in the field of Veterinary Science.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- Use of ICT in the area of Medical Science research and education.
- Identify the use and purpose of internet services in the libraries.
- Investigate the use of e-resources by the students of MMCHRI.
- Observe the attitude of the students of MMCHRI towards utilize of e-resources.
- Find out effective usage of e-resources in Medical Science.
- Recommend of measures for the development in presented library e-resources of Medical College.

Methodology

This study is based on survey method questionnaire tool was used. Structured questionnaire was distributed and collected data from the students of MMCHRI College, keeping in mind the basic objectives of the study. Data was collected from the students during the library visit of the college in the year 2018.

Data Analysis and Findings

63 (86.3%) questionnaires out of 87 students visited the Meenakshi Medical College Hospital & Research Institute, (MAHER-Deemed University) were received back. The data was collected through the structured questionnaires was analyzed, classified, and tabulated for well perceptible and clarity. The data was scrutinized and tabulated by used by suitable statistical methods.

Student Data

Out of 63 students, 35 (55.5 %) were male and 28 (44.4%) are female. Study shows that more male students were used by the library services than females.

Computer Knowledge of Medical Students

In the present computer era, efficient knowledge of computer has become necessity for all the students' purpose of their study. In this aspect, the present study makes an effort to determine the knowledge of computer amongst the students of medical colleges.

The study shows that all the U.G students were having basic efficient knowledge of computer, which is a good sign for any organization. The study found that the students are having ‘good knowledge’ of computers which has shown in Table 1. It shows that MMCHRI College is providing adequate computer training to the students to use all the existing e-resources.

Table Extent of Computer Knowledge

Extent	No. of Students(%)
Excellent	9(14.3%)
Very Good	23(36.5%)
Good	27(42.8 %)
Fair	2(3.2 %)
Satisfactory	2(3.2 %)
Total	63 (100 %)

Internet Usage

Now Internet has become an significant tool for education, research, and teaching. The information associated to all the fields is available on Internet, which is very useful for the students to enrich their knowledge. Present study makes an attempt to find out the make use of internet, frequency, purpose, and place of internet use.

Table 2 indicates that frequency of internet use by the students. Majority of the students, i.e., 32 (50.8 %) use internet daily, 36.5% of students use internet weekly, 6.3 % students use internet on fortnightly basis, a small percentage 1.6% student use internet once in month, while remaining 4.7 % students use internet as and when required.

Table Frequency of Internet Usage

Internet usage	No. of users (%)
Daily	32(50.8%)
Weekly	23(36.5 %)
Fortnightly	4 (6.3 %)
Monthly	1 (1.6 %)
As & when required	3 (4.7 %)
Total	63 (100 %)

Table 3 shows that 26 (41.3 %) of students used internet for ‘Downloading’, and about 15 (23.8 %) of students were used for ‘E.mail’ and 9(14.3%) of

students for ‘Chatting’purpose, a 12(9 %) of students used for ‘Research’, but very less used internet for ‘Entertainment’ which is fortunate, because the basic purpose of setting up of internet is fulfilled.

Table Purpose of Using Internet

Purpose of internet use	No. of responses (%)
Chatting	9(14.3 %)
E-Mail	15(23.8 %)
Research	12(9%)
Downloading	26(41.3 %)
Entertainment	1 (1.6 %)
Total	63 (100%)

Table 4 shows that; majority 53.9 % of students use internet in the library, 14 (22.2 %) use

Table Place for Internet Use

Place of internet use	No. of response (%)
Library	34(53.9%)
Department	14(22.2 %)
Home	9(14.3 %)
Any Other Place	6 (9.5 %)
Total	63(100 %)

Internet at ‘Department’, 14.3 % of students use at ‘Home’ and 95 % of students use for internet ‘Other Place’.

Awareness of e-resources

Table 5 shows that the level of awareness of e-resources amongst the students. 32(50.8%) of students were aware about Proquest online full text medical journal, the students who were aware of OPAC for services were 23.8 %, 14.3 % students have awareness of Open Access journals and only 11.1 % have awareness of DELNET (Developing Library Network).

Table Awareness of e-resources

E-resource	No. of response (%)
Proquest	32(50.8%)
Delnet	7 (11.1%)
Opent Access Journal	9(14.3%)
OPAC	15(23.8%)
Total	63(100%)

The information source for availability of e-resources was also collected from students. Table 6 shows that 31(49.2 %) / 8(12.7%) responses got information regarding e-resources from college library notice board/ circular, 12(19 %) got information from library staff, 12(19 %) responses got information from office circular, 1 (2.94 %) response got information from other sources.

Table Source of Available e-resources

E-resource	No. of response (%)
Proquest	32(50.8%)
Delnet	7 (11.1%)
Opent Access Journal	9(14.3%)
OPAC	15(23.8%)
Total	63(100%)

Table 7 shows that the students of MMCHRI used all the e-resources for their education. It shows that 42.8 % respondents were using e-journal, 18 % of the respondents using e-articles, 12 % respondents equally using e-book. 4.7% of the students were using e-thesis and other e-resources.

Table Frequency of e-resources use

E-resources	No. of response (%)
e-journal	27(42.8%)
e-articles	18 (28.5 %)
e-books	12 (19 %)
e-thesis/dissertation	3(4.7%)
All e-resources	3(4.7%)
Total	63 (100 %)

Analysis of e-resources data utilised by the students of MMCHRI shows that 32(88.9%) of respondents accessed for study purpose. A 9.5 % of respondents used for 'e-resources' for 'research and 4.4% seminar/workshop' purpose equally while 15.8 % of respondents for 'teaching' (Table 8).

Table Purpose of Using e-resources

Purpose of e-resources use	No. of response (%)
Study	32 (88.9 %)
Teaching	10 (15.8 %)
Research	6 (9.5 %)

Paper publication	9(14.3%)
Seminar/workshop presentation	4 (4.4 %)
All above	2(3.2%)
Total	63 (100%)

Criteria for Selection and Use of E-resources

Table 9 reveals the criteria for selection and use of e-resources. The majority 36.5 % of the respondents know the 'reliability' of e-resources and 33.3 % of the respondents feels that e-resources are 'usability'. Further, 19 % respondents opt for 'authenticity' and very low level percentage given the option for 'objectivity' and none of the students given any 'other criteria'.

Table Criteria for Selecting and Using E-Resource

Criteria for using e-resources	No. of response (%)
Reliability	23(36.5%)
Currency	2(3.2%)
Authenticity	12(19%)
Usability	21(33.3%)
Objectivity	5(7.9%)
Any other	0
Total	63(100%)

Reasons for Dissatisfaction on Available E-Resources

The reason for dissatisfaction on available e-resources at MMCHRI was also investigated and presented in Table 10. The study shows that the main reasons of dissatisfaction on the available e-resources. The majority 50.8 % of the students feels that print out facility is not satisfactory, further 19 % of students felt that the e-resources were not as per their needs and while 14.3 % of the responses noted that the timing of library 'not suitable'.

Table Reasons for Dissatisfaction on Available E-resources

Reasons of dissatisfaction	No. of response(%)
Printout facility not satisfactory	33(50.8%)
E-resources were not as per need	12(19%)

Library time not suitable	9 (14.3 %)
Library staffs were not Cooperative	2(3.2%)
Any other reasons	7(11.1%)
Total	63 (100 %)

Usefulness of E-resources

The study shows that the majority of students 2 (58.7%) think it is useful upto 'small extent'. 21 (33.6%) students say it is useful upto 'great extents' and rest 5 (7.9%) student says 'not at all useful' (Table 11).

Table Usefulness of e - Resources v/s Print Resources

Extent	No. of users (%)
Great extent	21 (33.3 %)
Small extent	37(58.7%)
Not at all useful	5 (7.9 %)
Total	63 (100 %)

Search Strategy of E-Resources

The opinion of 33 (52.4 %) responses was for easy accessibility of e-resources. Opinion of 23.8 %

Responses were for easily downloadable facility for e-resources, 3(4.7 %) responses was for archival facility for e-resources and 9 (14.3 %) response was for simultaneous usage of both (Table 12).

Table Advantages of Accessing e-Resources

Advantages	No. of response (%)
Availability of the journal much before the print copy	3(4.7%)
Simultaneous usage	9 (14.3 %)
Easy accessibility	33(52.4 %)
Downloading facility	15 (23.8%)
Author can be contacted directly through e-mail	0
Archival facility	3(4.7 %)
Total	63(100 %)

User Satisfaction with E-resources

The user satisfaction with e-resources was also studied. The study shows that 27 (42.8 %) students were partially satisfied with the service, further 18

(28.6 %) were fully satisfied, 11 (17.5 %) students were less satisfied and 7(11.1%) of student opted for 'not satisfied' for the e-service (Table 13).

Table Satisfaction with e-resource

Extent	No. of response (%)
Full satisfied	18(28.6 %)
Partially satisfied	27 (42.8 %)
Less satisfied	11 (17.5 %)
Not satisfied	7(11.1%)
Total	63 (100 %)

Users Visit to the Library for Services

The frequency of users visiting to the library for its services was also measured. The study shows that 36 (57.1 %) students visited library daily. This is a good sign for the library services. Further the 18 (28.5 %) students used for library services on weekly basis and 6 (9.5 %) students visited the library on fortnightly basis (Table 14).

Table Frequency of Library Visits

Extent	No. of response (%)
Full satisfied	18(28.6 %)
Partially satisfied	27 (42.8 %)
Less satisfied	11 (17.5 %)
Not satisfied	7(11.1%)
Total	63 (100 %)

Conclusion

It is clear from the findings that the MMCHRI under graduate students the service provided by the library is better, however at the same time they are expecting more than that. The majority of the students had visited the library on daily. This has a constructive mark, although some of the students had visited and utilized the services on weekly and by fortnightly basis as of their busy program or further associated works. The majority of the users were felt that e-resources have provided by the library to the huge amount is fulfill their necessities. E- Resources are require of the library is to meet out the necessities of target users. Here is requiring training the library staffs. Herein association the management has to provide a systematic training program for library

staff periodically. The user orientation programs are also to be included in the routine activity of the library. The student's attitude is seems to very positively towards using the e-resources for their study and research purpose. Libraries are plays to vital role as gateway to access of e-resources and it provides supports to accessing the e-resources. The undergraduate medical students are mostly dependents on e-resources used for their essential information and to remain up-to-date with their subject area. Some more computers are should be increased in the library for accessing e-databases and make using other e-resources. The study makes known that the undergraduate medical students of MMCHRI College are using the available e -resources pleasingly.

References

- Swain, D K & Panda, K C, "Use of e-services by faculty members of business schools in a state of India: A study. Collection Building", vol. 28 no.3, pp.108-16, 2009. <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/> (accessed on 5 November 2009).
- Satapathy, Sunil Kumar & Rout Biswanath. Use of e-resources by the faculty members with special reference to CVRCE, Bhubaneswar, *DESIDOC J. Lib. Inf. Technol.*, 2010, 30(4), 11-16.
- K.N. Kandpal*, S.S. Rawat* and K.S.R. Vithal Use of E-resources by Undergraduate Students of NTR College of Veterinary Science, Andhra Pradesh *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, Vol. 33, No. 5, September 2013, pp. 394-398.